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ABSTRACT BOOK

Posters

Comminuted Distal Tibia Fractures Treated with Ilizarov Technique

Ivica Lalić¹, Vladimir Harhaji¹, Oliver Dulić², Aleksandar Božović³, Slađan Timotijević⁴

¹University Business Academy In Novi Sad Faculty Of Pharmacy, Novi Sad, , Serbia, ²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia, Clinical Center of Vojvodina, Clinic for Orthopedic Surgery and Traumatology, Novi Sad, , Serbia, ³Faculty of Medicine, University of Priština in Kosovska Mitrovica, Surgery Clinic, Department of Orthopedics and Traumatology, Clinical Hospital Center Kosovska Mitrovica, , , Serbia, ⁴Clinical Hospital Center “Bežanijska kosa” , Belgrade, , Serbia

SUMMARY

Introduction: High-energy distal tibia fractures are characterized by great comminution and extensive lesions of surrounding soft tissues. The risk of developing complications during treatment is high.

Methods: In the study were included 41 patients. Clinical characteristics were evaluated during Gustillo-Anderson, Checketts-Otterburns, and AO/OTA classification. The ASAMI protocol is used to assess bone union. Functional treatment results were represented using a modified Karlström-Ollerud scoring system.

Results: Using radiographic and clinical parameters, we recorded complete healing in all fractures. In intra-articular fractures group 43B, the circular fixator was removed after 16 weeks (range 13-31), while in fracture type 43C group, it was removed after 18 weeks (range 13-29). The ASAMI evaluation of bone healing showed: 31 (75%) excellent, 76 (15%) good, 3 (8%) satisfactory, and 1 (2%) poor results. Functional recovery results present after 6 months showed us a mean value of 24.7 using a modified Karlström-Ollerud scoring system in three follow-up periods, which represents recovery. Results presented 12 months after surgery showed a mean value of 27.6, representing satisfactory recovery, while during the last parameter measurement performed after 18 months, the value was 29.5, which indicates good functional recovery.

Conclusion: Transosseous osteosynthesis Ilizarov treatment applied in closed and open comminuted distal tibia fractures showed good final bone and function results with minimal complications.

Keywords: Ilizarov technique, distal tibia fractures, comminuted fractures, ASAMI classification